

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

STUDYING WELL-BEING IN GERIATRIC PSYCHOLOGY: THEORETICAL AND EMPIRICAL APPROACHES

Abdullayeva Z.

PhD student

Baku State University, Department of Gender and Applied Psychology

Baku, Azerbaijan

orcid.org/0009-0009-0820-2911

ABSTRACT

Developing as an independent science, the social psychology of aging has a very short history in our country. It has a longer history abroad. Therefore, it is difficult to find "ready-made" forms of knowledge when we are currently witnessing the formation of entirely new principles and approaches, their implementation in the practice of socio-psychological and developmental psychology research. However, no truth here is absolute. Moreover, the question arises about the right of social psychology of aging to exist as an independent scientific discipline, especially since methodology, research methods, and even terminology are undergoing refinement and agreement. Many questions relate to the fields of social gerontology, social psychology, social work theory, and other disciplines. The very phrase "social psychology of aging" indicates the specific place this discipline occupies in the system of scientific knowledge. Having emerged at the intersection of sciences—psychology, sociology, and gerontology—the psychology of aging retains its special status, meaning that each of these disciplines includes it as an integral part. Moreover, the problems of old age are studied not only by psychologists, sociologists, and physicians, but also by economists, demographers, political scientists, educators, social workers, and others.

Keywords: mental health, wellbeing, aging, gerontology, psychological factors.

The rapid increase in the number of elderly people as a result of global demographic changes in the 21st century has brought the issue of well-being to the forefront in the field of geriatric psychology. Indeed, if we look at the statistical indicators of recent years, we will observe a significant increase in the number of elderly people. This can be observed both in the world and in our country. According to the State Statistics Committee, by the beginning of 2024, the number of citizens aged 70 and over in the country was 500.9 thousand people. This constitutes 4.9 percent of the total population (SSC). According to UN estimates, by 2050, the number of people over 65 years old in the world will more than double. These demographic changes create new demands not only on the healthcare system, but also on psychosocial intervention strategies. The concept of well-being has been at the center of psychological literature for many years. In traditional approaches, well-being was explained mainly in terms of hedonic (happiness, satisfaction) aspects. In later periods, the concept of eudaimonic (meaningful life, self-actualization, psychological development) well-being came to the fore (Ryff, 2014). These theoretical approaches led to the development of various instruments in geriatric psychology to measure the quality of life of older people. Psychological well-being includes many factors such as the ability to cope with stressful situations in a person's life, as well as the ability to experience positive emotions, self-actualization, and success in social relationships. Studies show that people with a high level of well-being are distinguished by their social behavior and positive, friendly relationships in society. They spend their days more productively, with a higher level of self-confidence, increased creativity, effective activity, working, learning, and making more efforts towards their goals (Huppert, 2013).

WHO classifies the main elements of mental health protection in older people as follows.

- Steps aimed at reducing economic inequality
- Social support for older people and their caregivers
- Healthy and proper nutrition, physical activity, and not using tobacco and alcohol
- Developing medical and social programs to help people living alone, living in remote areas, and those with chronic diseases
- Creating safe places and programs to connect (WHO 2023).

Governments and organizations should have the means to further improve the coping with stressful situations of people caring for their elderly parents (Valiant, 2002).

The action plan signed by WHO member states aims to protect the older generation. People working with older people can use this program for diagnostic and treatment purposes (WHO).

In the sciences of geriatrics and gerontology, we see that the concept of positive aging has come to the fore (Hill, 2011). Although concepts such as healthy and successful aging (Paul and Ribeiro, 2015; Estebansari et al., 2020) are used in scientific literature, positive aging is expressed as a more comprehensive concept that includes other concepts (Lam et al., 2020; Bar-Tur, 2021). In addition to the fact that the elderly population lives longer, topics such as increasing their level of well-being, quality of life, and taking steps to support their positive aging are gaining increasing importance (Denmark and Zarbiv, 2016; Bar-Tur, 2021).

A healthier aging environment is formed in a society where older people feel that their thoughts on life and life satisfaction are protected. (Li&He, 2023).

According to scientific research predictions for the future, the education level of the elderly population will increase further in the next 20–25 years. Their ability to use technological innovations will increase further (J.C.Cavanaugh & F. B. Field, 2018). Research has shown the need for a more in-depth study of the well-being of older adults. The following measurement tools are often used in scientific research.

1. CASP-19 (Hyde et al., 2003)
 - Designed to assess quality of life in early old age.
 - Measures four main domains: control, independence, self-actualization, and happiness.
 - Widely used to understand the subjective well-being of older people.
 - WHOQOL-OLD (Power et al., 2005)
 - A module developed by the World Health Organization.
 - Covers domains such as social participation, intimate relationships, emotional well-being, and attitudes toward death.
 - Suitable for use in multicultural contexts.
 - OPQOL and OPQOL-brief (Bowling, 2009; Bowling & Stenner, 2011)
 - Assesses daily life satisfaction, social relationships, and health status in older people.
 - The short version (OPQOL-brief) is more commonly used in practical research.
4. Ryff's Psychological Well-Being Model (Ryff, 2014)
 - Measures self-acceptance, personal growth, independence, purpose in life, positive relationships, and control over the environment.
 - One of the most widely used models in the study of eudaimonic well-being in older people. Literature analysis shows that well-being is closely related not only to individual psychological factors, but also to the social environment. Community support, family relationships, and access to health services are the main determinants of psychological well-being in older people. Although instruments such as CASP-19 and OPQOL are effective in measuring subjective well-being, they create limitations in research if they are not adapted to the cultural environment of the country.

Geriatric psychology in Azerbaijan is still at a nascent stage of development. In this regard, the adaptation of existing international measurement tools to the Azerbaijani language and psychometric validation are of particular importance for the effectiveness of future research.

Conclusion: The study of well-being in geriatric psychology draws on theoretical approaches such as hedonic theory, desire theory, and goal list theory, as well as empirical research using observational methods, testing, longitudinal studies, and other psychological techniques. Empirical research helps test theoretical models and assess various aspects of well-being in older adults, for example, using instruments such as the

Ryff Well-Being Scale, WHO QOL scale, and other valid sources.

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